

THE ROLE OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS IN THE FORMATION OF LEADERSHIP QUALITIES

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Abstract. *This article scientifically analyzes the role and significance of socio-psychological factors in forming leadership qualities in managers. It was also shown that the development of leadership competencies is one of the priority areas of state policy, and it is also noted that emotional intelligence, social support, collective values, and national traditions in leadership serve the effective formation of leadership qualities.*

Keywords: *leadership, socio-psychological factors, emotional intelligence, state policy, motivation, communication.*

Introduction

Today, global changes taking place on a global scale in the socio-economic and scientific-technical spheres require new approaches to the formation of leadership qualities in managers. Due to the fact that the content of modern management, the requirements, character, and directions of leadership activity are constantly improving, the role of socio-psychological factors in the process of developing leadership qualities is of particular importance. Because the social competence of the leader's personality, the ability to communicate effectively with the team, socio-emotional intelligence, and conflict management skills are the main factors determining their leadership potential.

New andragogical and eutagogical paradigms, as well as competency-based approaches, reveal the decisive role of the socio-psychological environment in the personal and professional development of managers. In particular, as emphasized at the Council of Europe Symposium on "Basic Competencies for Europe," the development of leadership, communicative, social partnership, and creativity competencies of leaders provides important advantages in team management.

Therefore, in-depth study of socio-psychological factors in the process of forming leadership qualities in managers, their effective implementation in management activities, and comprehensive support for the leader's personality remain relevant issues.

As the President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, noted, "All of us, especially leaders, need deep knowledge, intelligence, and patience..."

Indeed, in recent years, special attention has been paid in the Republic of Uzbekistan to increasing leadership potential and developing effective management and leadership competencies. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, No. UP-60, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," defined the legal basis for reforms aimed at modernizing the management system and developing human capital in our country [1].

It shows the relevance of developing not only professional but also psychological and social competencies in leadership activities. Consequently, the study of socio-psychological

factors determining the formation of leadership qualities in leaders is an important issue from a scientific and practical point of view.

Literature review

In foreign literature, the formation of leadership qualities is explained by the interaction of personal qualities, the social environment, and psychological factors. In the theory of transformational leadership, B. Bass emphasizes that the charisma of the leader and methods of intellectual motivation increase the effectiveness of the team [2]. D. Goleman, on the other hand, considers emotional intelligence as the central competence of effective leadership [3]. J. Storey connects leadership effectiveness with the socio-psychological environment in the organization [4]. In her research, M. Yuliyeva emphasized that leadership qualities are connected not only with innate personality traits but also with social situations and environment [5]. This approach became the basis for viewing leadership as a contextual process. In his work, J. Burns put forward the concept of transformational leadership, emphasizing that the goal of a leader is to inspire individuals, direct them towards high values, and prepare them for innovative changes [6]. Uzbek scientists have also conducted research in this area, substantiating the importance of psychological stability, responsibility, and national values in leadership [7].

Also, the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 defines the need to improve the competencies of managerial personnel, strengthen their psychological training, and introduce modern management approaches [1].

Research methodology

This study is based on the method of theoretical and conceptual analysis and existing scientific literature on the research topic. The results of international research and educational policy documents were studied, and the legislation, resolutions, and decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan were analyzed. When writing the article, the method of bibliographic analysis was used, leadership theories were studied, and interviews were conducted with leaders of various levels and their teams using questionnaires and interview methods. Also, with the help of observation methods, it was observed that managers use socio-psychological factors in real management practice. The conclusions presented in the article have a theoretical basis and are formed through a deductive approach.

Analysis and Results

According to the results of the conducted research, the following socio-psychological factors play an important role in the formation of leadership qualities in managers:

1) Emotional intelligence. In the modern management process, not only the intellectual potential of the leader's personality but also his emotional intelligence is of great importance. Emotional intelligence is an individual's ability to understand, manage, and effectively utilize their own and others' emotions [8]. In leadership activity, this ability is a decisive factor in the formation of leadership qualities. The main components of emotional intelligence—self-awareness, self-management, motivation, empathy, and social skills—increase the effectiveness of a leader's management. In particular, empathy and a culture of communication contribute to the creation of a trusting atmosphere in the team, while self-control and stress resistance contribute to the constructive resolution of contradictions.

Studies show that leaders with high emotional intelligence are more successful in motivating employees, mobilizing the team towards a common goal, and making innovative decisions [3]. From this point of view, emotional intelligence manifests itself as an important

socio-psychological factor in the formation of not only professional but also personal leadership qualities of a leader.

2) Self-awareness of the individual. In the process of forming leadership qualities in managers, among socio-psychological factors, self-awareness of the individual is of great importance. Self-awareness is a person's ability to correctly perceive their emotions, personal capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses [9]. The better a leader knows himself, the more consciously he can control his actions in the management process. The level of self-awareness of the leader's personality plays a decisive role in decision-making, maintaining stability in stressful situations, and establishing effective communication with the team. A high level of self-awareness allows the leader to develop leadership qualities through critical thinking, proper distribution of responsibility, and self-assessment of their activities.

3) Group dynamics and social influence. Leadership is not the action of an individual but the result of group interaction processes. The leader's behavior and communication style directly affect group relationships, trust between employees, and overall effectiveness. According to social learning theory, employees can acquire leadership skills by observing the behavior of their managers.

4) Organizational culture. In the process of forming leadership qualities, organizational culture manifests itself as an important socio-psychological factor. Organizational culture is a set of values, norms, behavioral principles, and management traditions adopted by team members. The leader's ability to correctly form this culture contributes to a healthy social environment in the team, increasing the motivation and loyalty of employees. A strong organizational culture strengthens the leader's leadership reputation. Because in a team formed on the basis of common values, an atmosphere of cooperation, trust, and openness prevails. In this process, the leader acts as an exemplary person and develops leadership qualities through his fair decisions, communication culture, and attention to the team.

There are also several other socio-psychological factors, and the mechanisms of social support, that is, the education and professional development systems created by the state, in particular, the training and retraining programs of managerial personnel carried out at the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, serve to improve the knowledge and skills of managers, as well as strengthen their leadership qualities.

Moreover, the culture of communication and communication are considered important socio-psychological factors in increasing the authority and prestige of the leader. The establishment of open and constructive communication within the team strengthens the leader's credibility. This aspect is consistent with the initiatives of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, "dialogue with the people" and "open dialogue," and requires effective communication between leaders and the community and citizens [10].

In addition, motivational factors also play a decisive role in the formation of leadership qualities in managers. The system of material and moral incentives established by the state encourages managers to strive for innovation, be proactive, and lead the team towards a common goal.

The above-mentioned factors further strengthen the leadership potential of managers and increase management efficiency.

Discussion

The obtained results are consistent with international theories. Theories of transformational leadership and emotional intelligence consider personal and psychological factors important in the

formation of leadership qualities. Our analysis showed that in the conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this process is provided with a legal and institutional basis through state decrees and resolutions. In particular, in the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," tasks aimed at improving leadership competencies and developing socio-psychological training are inextricably linked with international theories.

In future research, it is also important to study the features of the formation of leadership qualities in women leaders, taking into account the factors of gender equality. It is also necessary to conduct a scientific assessment of the effectiveness of state support systems and professional development programs created for managers. In addition to this, the experimental study of the influence of psychological trainings, coaching, and mentoring technologies on the development of leadership qualities acquires scientific and practical significance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, socio-psychological factors play a decisive role in the formation of leadership qualities in managers. Emotional intelligence, personal self-awareness, understanding of group dynamics, and the ability to adapt to organizational culture are among the main competencies of an effective leader. The results of this study prove that when developing leadership development programs, it is necessary to pay attention not only to the development of knowledge but also to the development of socio-psychological skills.

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